

Functional Outcome of Congenital Talipes Equinovarus (CTEV) Treated by Conventional Ponseti Technique versus Accelerated Ponseti Technique: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background: Congenital talipes equinovarus (clubfoot) occurs in one in 1000 live births and is one of the most common birth defects involving the musculoskeletal system. Ponseti method involves weekly manipulation of the deformity followed by a long-leg cast is the time proven method of management. Modified accelerated treatment protocols were designed to reduce the total duration of treatment involved in correcting deformity. This study was conducted to compare the functional outcome of CTEV achieved between conventional and accelerated Ponseti methods.

Methods: A two-arm prospective study was conducted with participants randomized to two groups- Study group and Control groups. A total of 60 children (30 in each group was participated). All feet were scored using Pirani score, recorded by an independent assessor at each visit. Plaster treatment was continued until clinical correction achieved. The data was collected using pre-structured proforma and analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation, Chi square and unpaired t test.

Results: There were 65% males ins study group and 60% males in control group with a mean age of 12.5±5.35 weeks and 10.86±6.21 weeks respectively for control and study group. Accelerated Ponseti technique has relatively shorter duration of manipulation compared to the standard Ponseti technique and it was statistically significant (0.001). Total number of casts used is not significantly different for accelerated Ponseti technique compared to the standard Ponseti technique.

Conclusion: Accelerated Ponseti technique for club foot management was equally effective compared to the standard Ponseti technique in managing idiopathic congenital talipes equinovarus with relatively shorter duration of manipulation compared to the standard Ponseti technique. Total number of casts used was not significantly different for accelerated Ponseti technique effectiveness compared to the standard Ponseti technique.

Keywords: Congenital talipes equinovarus; Ponseti method; Accelerated Ponseti method, CTEV.

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Introduction

Idiopathic congenital talipes equinovarus (CTEV), also known as clubfoot, has been a recognized deformity since the time of the ancient Egyptians and was independently described by both Hippocrates and the Aztecs and it is the most common congenital foot disorder. [1]

The incidence of CTEV is 5–6 per 1000 live births, varying with race and geography. The goal of any type of CTEV management is to reduce, if not to eliminate all elements of the clubfoot deformity,

hence achieving a functional, pain free, normal looking plantigrade, mobile, callous free, and normal shoe able foot. [2]

Many treatment methods are described for the management of clubfoot, ranging from strapping, stretching & casting, surgical release of soft tissues, bony procedures and finally arthrodesis. The various factors that have been associated with the poor prognosis in CTEV management are female child, hereditary, late age of presentation, severity

of deformity, rigidity of foot, associated cavus, associated clawing of toes, and small heel [1,2]

Initial treatment options all were variations on manipulation and splinting. In 1930, Kite popularized gentle manipulation and serial casting by conservative methods, which remains the initial treatment of choice. [3]

The first description of the Ponseti technique was published in 1963; 15 years after, Ponseti had actually begun using this method. Popularity of the technique spread by time resulted in a great decrease in the rate of extensive clubfoot surgery. Ponseti method involves weekly manipulation of the deformity followed by a long-leg cast. It takes about 4–5 weeks to correct all components of the deformity with the exception of the equinus. [4-6]

Shortening the correction time is required for patients travelling long distances seeking for treatment; decreased correction time offers a financial gain for the parents. In addition, keeping a plaster clean and dry for one week can be challenging especially for parents with limited literacy. Modified accelerated treatment protocols were designed: 5- day protocol developed by Morcuende et al. which included manipulation and casting every 5 days instead of the traditional 7-day protocol and twice weekly protocol by Xu who did manipulation and casting twice a week; they found that the feet were corrected at a significantly shorter time as compared to the traditional protocol with equivalent outcomes. [6,7]

There is only limited evidence available regarding the comparison of Ponseti technique with accelerated Ponseti technique especially among the Indian population. Hence, a comparative study was conducted to determine effectiveness of a shorter duration of treatment-accelerated Ponseti Method with standard Ponseti method for treatment of idiopathic clubfoot as assessed by Pirani scoring system.

Methodology

Study Design: A two-arm prospective study.

Study Setting: The department of Orthopedics, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Bengaluru.

Study Duration: 18 Months (November 2022-May 2024)

Study Population: Children less than two years who were diagnosed as Idiopathic CTEV were included in the study who were attending the department of Orthopedics, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Bengaluru during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria: Children less than two years who were diagnosed as Idiopathic CTEV and who were willing to participate were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with Syndromic club foot, secondary club foot, previously operated club foot, previously treated with a casting technique, neglected or relapsed clubfoot, who are unfit or non-complaint to the prescribed technique were excluded from the study.

Sample Size: A total of 60 patients (30 in each group) was selected for the study.

Sampling Method

Simple random sampling method was used to allocate the participants into two groups. Random allocation sequence was generated using online tool www.randomizer.com, with 1:1 allocation and SNOSE (Sequentially Numbered, Opaque, Sealed Envelope) was used to implement the random allocation sequence. Generation of the random allocation sequence, enrolling and assigning participants to interventions were carried out by people who have no clinical involvement in the trial (blinding) to avoid investigator's bias.

Ethical Clearance: The ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethics committee and data was collected after the informed written consent from the parents.

Data collection and Intervention: The data was collected from the parents after they gave informed written consent to be part of the study and after understanding that they can be put in any of the two-intervention arms randomly.

After the randomization of the participants into two groups (Standard Ponseti and Accelerated Ponseti Method) all the feet were scored using Pirani method,⁸ recorded by an independent assessor at each visit. Plaster treatment was continued until clinical correction achieved. A percutaneous tendo achillis tenotomy was performed if dorsiflexion is $<10^\circ$ at the end of manipulation and plastering. Both groups were put into plaster, following tenotomy, for three weeks. The defined endpoint of treatment for both groups, labeled 'treatment time in plaster' refers to the number of days in plaster prior to a tenotomy.

Within the accelerated group we defined failure as a Pirani score of >1.0 at 21 days of plaster treatment. Both groups were given abduction braces to wear for three years following their plaster treatment, 23 hours per day for the first three months followed by night time bracing until the child's third birthday, in accordance with the standard local Ponseti programme. All patients were treated as out patients, thereby reducing any bias from altered compliance and enabling us to directly compare the efficacy of the two methods in terms of correction

of the deformity.

Data collection proforma: A structured proforma was designed to collect the data. It consisted of two parts: The first part included participant's demographic profile, medical history and clinical examinations. Second part included details about operative procedures and Pirani Scoring at different follow-ups.

Statistical Analysis: Data collected were entered in a MS Excel sheet. The descriptive and analytical statistics were performed using with the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 software. Percentages, means and standard deviations (SD) were computed for descriptive purposes. Student t test was used to compare the mean of age, number of casts and Pirani Score between study group and comparison group. Chi Square test was used to compare frequency distributions between the two groups. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

A two-arm prospective study was conducted to compare the efficacy of accelerated Ponseti with

standard Ponseti technique in a tertiary care center, Bengaluru. A total of 60 participants (30 participants in standard Ponseti (Control group) and accelerated Ponseti technique (Study group)) were participated and study had 100% subject retention in both the groups from baseline to follow up. There was a total of 40 feet samples included per group from 30 subjects for the intervention. There were 65% males among the samples in study group and 60% males in control group. Among 40 samples of control group, 52.5% were in the age group of 1-12 weeks, and 47.5% were in the age group of 13-24 weeks. Among 40 samples of study group, 60% were in the age group of 1-12 weeks, and 40% were in the age group of 13-24 weeks and with mean age of 12.5±5.35 weeks (control group) and 10.86±6.21 weeks (study group). There were 25% bilateral and 75% unilateral samples among the study group and control group. Only 7.5% controls had less than 28 days correction time and among control group, mean duration of correction was 35.68±5.44 days while it was 19.30±3.91 days, in study group (Table 1).

Table 1: Basic Demographic and Clinical Details of the participants

Characteristics	Standard Ponseti Method (Control Group; N=40 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti Method (Study Group N=40 feet)
Gender		
• Male	26 (65.0%)	24 (60.0%)
• Female	14 (35.0%)	16 (40.0%)
Age Group		
• 01-12 weeks	21 (52.5%)	24 (60.0%)
• 13-24 weeks	19 (47.5%)	16 (40.0%)
Side of anomaly		
• Bilateral	10 (25.0%)	10 (25.0%)
• Unilateral	30 (75.0%)	30 (75.0%)
Duration from start of correction till tenotomy		
• Less than 28 days	03 (07.5%)	38 (95.0%)
• More than 28 days	37 (92.5%)	02 (05.0%)

Majority (55%) of the samples in the control group needed 5 casts to complete the procedure followed by 27.5% with 4 casts and among the study group, 42.5% needed 6 casts, 27.5% needed 5 casts. 70% of the samples in the control group had an initial Pirani score of 5 followed by 17.5% with a score of 6. Among the study group, 55% had an initial Pirani score of 5 followed by 32.5% with a score of 6.

In the control group 52.5% of the samples had a final Pirani score of 0, while 47.5% had a score of 1. Among the study group, 57.5% had a final Pirani score of 0, while 42.5% had a score of 1. Majority of the samples in control group (67.5%) and study group (65%) were undergone tenotomy and the difference between the groups was not statistically significant (p=0.9). (Table 2)

Table 2: Clinical details and Pirani Score among the two groups

Characteristics	Standard Ponseti Method (Control Group; N=40 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti Method (Study Group N=40 feet)
Number of casts required		
• 3	03 (07.5%)	0
• 4	11 (27.5%)	06 (15.0%)
• 5	22 (55.0%)	11 (27.5%)
• 6	04 (10.0%)	17 (42.5%)

• 7	0	05 (12.5%)
• 8	0	01 (02.5%)
Pre-intervention Pirani Score		
• 4	05 (12.5%)	05(12.5%)
• 5	28 (70.0%)	22 (55.0%)
• 6	07 (17.5%)	13 (32.5%)
Final Pirani Score after intervention		
• 0	21 (52.5%)	23 (57.5%)
• 1	19 (47.5%)	17 (42.5%)
Tenotomy Performed		
• Yes	13 (32.5%)	14 (35.0%)
• No	27 (67.5%)	26 (65.0%)

Among control group, mean number of casts used was 4.91 ± 0.74 while it was 5.2 ± 0.94 in study group. There was no statistically significant difference ($p=0.076$) between the groups regarding number of casts used. Among control group, mean duration for correction till tenotomy was 35.68 ± 5.44

days while it was 19.30 ± 3.91 days in the study group and the difference was statistically significant ($p=0.001$).

So, the number of days required for correction was less in accelerated Ponseti method compared to standard method. (Table 3)

Table 3: Comparison of Clinical and Pirani Score among the two groups

Characteristics	Standard Ponseti Method (Mean \pm SD)	Accelerated Ponseti Method (Mean \pm SD)	P value
Number of Casts	4.91 ± 0.74	5.2 ± 0.94	0.076
Duration from start of correction till tenotomy (Days)	35.68 ± 5.44	19.30 ± 3.91	0.001
Pre-intervention Pirani Score	5.06 ± 0.52	5.19 ± 0.67	0.317
Final Pirani Score after intervention	0.48 ± 0.506	0.43 ± 0.501	0.658

The initial Pirani score before the intervention between control group and study group were 5.06 ± 0.52 and 5.19 ± 0.67 respectively and there was no statistical difference between the groups. The mean final Pirani score between the control group and study group were 0.48 ± 0.506 and 0.43 ± 0.501 respectively and there was no statistical difference between the groups (Table 3).

Complications of tight cast was observed in one child in control group because of lack of proper foot end elevation instructions followed by the parents and one child had come with recurred deformity at 5 months follow-up due non-compliance towards brace for which three more corrective casting was done in control group. No participants had developed excoriation of skin both in control and study groups.

Discussion

Congenital talipes equinovarus, also referred to as clubfoot, occurs in one in 1000 live births and is one of the most common birth defects involving the musculoskeletal system. It consists of four components: Ankle equines, hindfoot varus, forefoot adductus, and midfoot cavus.⁹ Although clubfoot is recognizable at birth, the severity of the deformity can vary from mild to an extremely rigid foot that is resistant to manipulation.¹⁰ When untreated, children with clubfoot walk on the sides and/or tops of their feet, resulting in callus

formation, potential skin and bone infections, inability to wear standard shoes, and substantial limitations in mobility and employment opportunities. [11]

Surgeons have struggled over the years to identify the best method of treatment for the congenital clubfoot deformity. This struggle has lessened over the last decade as the Ponseti method of clubfoot manipulation and casting, Achilles tendon tenotomy, and foot abduction bracing has become the primary treatment for idiopathic clubfoot around the world. [12]

Age: Age is an important parameter to consider while discussing any surgical corrective technique for a congenital anomaly. However, the Ponseti method was applied with equal success in children younger and older than 6 months. [13]

Study done by Sharma P et al (2016) had mean age of 23.54 ± 11.54 days in the accelerated group and 22.95 ± 11.12 days in the conventional group which was not statically significant. [14] The current study had comparable distribution of age groups between the groups. The difference between the mean age 12.5 ± 5.35 and $10. \pm 6.21$ for conventional and accelerated group respectively, was also not significant. Hence the important demographic factor-age is matched between the groups.

Gender: Idiopathic clubfoot has been widely reported to affect males more frequently than

females. [15] The results are in line with this evidence where the majority of the participants were males in our study.

According to Gillani SF et al, there were 61.3% male out of 80 Patients in their study. [16] According to Solanki M et al, [19] were male (57.69 %) and 12 female (42.30%) showing male preponderance. [17] Our study had 65% male in control group and 60% male in study group. Hence the results are correlated with male preponderance.

Manifestation of anomaly: Traditionally, idiopathic unilateral and bilateral clubfoot are considered to have similar characteristics and have been classified within the same group for scientific research. As per the epidemiological evidence, 50% of all the cases are bilateral in manifestation. [18] According to Sharma et al, out of total 40 patients they had 13 bilateral cases (35%). Our study also demonstrated similar prevalence ratio of bilateral clubfoot among both groups but it was less compared to study done by Harnett p et al, [21] cases were bilateral out of 40 cases (52.5%). [4,14,19].

Duration for correction in days: In Ponseti technique, the clubfoot is manipulated and fixated in a corrected position using a plaster cast. This cast is typically changed every week. Duration of the procedure was a concern from the inception of Ponseti technique. In low-income countries this can be especially important if practitioners are scarce and patients live far away from the hospital. [20]

The reason for having a weekly treatment interval seems to be largely pragmatic. Clustering patients on one fixed day of the week is convenient for hospital planning and makes it easier to organize the necessary care around a newborn. Additionally, accommodating all clubfoot patients on a single day gives parents the opportunity to share their concerns with other parents. [21] Shortening the interval time could be advantageous for several reasons. Parents who do not have ready access to treatment facilities may have to leave home for the treatment duration. For those who can make outpatient visits to a clinic, shortening the treatment time will reduce the time during which their family life is interrupted. [22]

According to Harnett p et al, the median number of treatment days in plaster was 16 in the accelerated group and 42 days in the control group ($p < 0.001$) which was statistically significant. [19] According to Sharma P et al, the average duration of treatment in the accelerated was 15 days whereas in the conventional method was 35 days ($p < 0.05$) which was statistically significant. [14]

In our study, most of the subjects in the Ponseti technique group had a longer duration (35.68 ± 5.44) of treatment compared to the accelerated Ponseti

technique group (19.30 ± 3.91) and the difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.01$). This proves the advantage of accelerated Ponseti technique over the traditional Ponseti technique with respect to the convenience of the subjects in terms of shorter duration.

Number of casts used: The current study doesn't show a significant difference in number of casts used between the groups. The study group (accelerated Ponseti technique) had used (5.2 ± 0.94) a greater number of casts compared to the other group (4.91 ± 0.74) which is in line with some of the previous studies. [14,23] and in contrast with the other studies. [17,24] However the difference between the groups regarding mean number of casts used was not significant ($P = 0.076$).

According to Gillani SF et al the mean number of casts required was 5.2 in group A and 5.12 in group B out of 80 patients which was not statistically significant. [16] According to Sahu B et al, the average number of casts required for correction was 6.2 in accelerated group and 8.2 in standard group which was significant. [24]

Pirani Score: The study used Pirani Score as the measure of success of the treatment. There was no significant difference between the groups regarding Pirani Score in baseline (5.06 ± 0.52 and 5.19 ± 0.67 for control and study group respectively) and final score (0.48 ± 0.51 and 0.43 ± 0.506 for control and study group respectively) which proves that both the techniques are equally effective ($P = 0.317$ and $P = 0.658$ for initial and final Pirani scoring). This finding was similar with previous studies [4, 5,14,17,20,24] According to Harnett P et al, the initial median Pirani score was 5.5 in the accelerated group and 5.0 in the standard control group. There was no significant difference in the final Pirani score between the two groups, $P = 0.308$. [19]

According to Sahu B et al, average initial pirani score was 5.03 and 5.3 in standard and accelerated group respectively. The average final pirani score was 0.2 and 0.25 in standard and accelerated ponsetti group respectively which was not statically significant. [24]

Tenotomy: A percutaneous tendo achillis tenotomy was performed if dorsiflexion is < 10 at the end of manipulation and plastering. Both groups were put into plaster, following tenotomy, for three weeks. There was no difference between the groups regarding the number of subject undergone tenotomy. We had 13(32.5%) and 14(35%) feet undergone tenotomy out of total 40 feet in each control and study group and it was less compared to study done by Solanki M et al [17] (tendoachillies tenotomy was required in 65% feet in accelerated group and 55% in standard group which statically insignificant ($P = 0.56$)).

According to the best evidence synthesis, no evidence exists to support the use of a cast change interval of one week. It can be concluded that the accelerated versions of the Ponseti method can safely be used in the treatment of clubfoot without risking any significant increase in the required number of casts.

Limitations: The study was conducted in a government hospital, the participants were mainly from the lower socioeconomic strata of society. This will limit interpretations and the possibilities of generalization. Also, we included patients less than 2 years of age. This may be the limiting factor in age.

Conclusions

Accelerated Ponseti technique for club foot management was equally effective compared to the standard Ponseti technique in managing idiopathic congenital talipes equinovarus with relatively shorter duration of manipulation compared to the standard Ponseti technique. Total number of casts used was not significantly different for accelerated Ponseti technique effectiveness compared to the standard Ponseti technique.

Recommendations: Longitudinal long term follows up studies are required to establish a better evidence and influence of relapse. Accelerated Ponseti technique is effective in treating idiopathic CTEV. Hence, may be used as preferred method for routine practice in correction of CTEV. However, further studies with large sample size with different settings and more duration of follow up is necessary to generalize the study findings to the larger population.

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